

ISic3717

I.Sicily inscription 3717

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary (?)

Material

marble (white veined)

Object

tabula

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Agrigentum

Place of origin (modern)

Agrigento

Provenance

found in the catacombs

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Agrigento, Museo Regionale
Archeologico Pietro Griffo

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: EDR136048

0. [---]

1. [---]ιο ι [---]

2. [---] Σίμων ν [---]

3. [---] κίου, φυλη [ς ---]

4. [---] ἐν Ἀκράγα [ντι ---]

5.

Edition: PHI336053

1. [— — — — — — — — — — —]

2. [— — — —]ΙΟ Ι [— — — — — —]

3. [— — —] Σίμων ν [— — — —]

4. [— — —] κίου, φυλή [ς — — —]

5. [— — —] ἐν Ἀκράγ α [ντι — —]

6. [— — — — — — — — — — —]

7.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

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Bibliography

1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum graecum*. At 49.1266.9

Manganaro, G. 1999. Sikelika: studi di antichità e di epigrafia della Sicilia greca. Pisa, Roma. At 37 no.9 fig.86

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